

A P O L L O

D6.2: 1st APOLLO TRAINING MATERIAL

WP6 – Pilot operation and evaluation

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Table of Contents

Executive summary	Error! Bookmark not defined.
1 Introduction	5
2 Content of training material	6
3 Annexes	7
Annex I: Get started with APOLLO	7
Annex II: User Guide “How to register an APOLLO account”	8
Annex III: User Guide “How to log in your APOLLO account”	11
Annex IV: User Guide “How to edit profile settings”	13
Annex V: User Guide “How to add your parcels to APOLLO platform”	19
Annex VI: User Guide “How to use APOLLO services”	24

Executive summary

This document reports on the development of the first set of APOLLO training material within the context of the Task 6.2 Pilot training and execution. The current set of training material reflects the functionalities of APOLLO platform beta version and supports execution of beta phase of the pilots.

1 Introduction

One of the main objectives in Apollo project is to offer high quality services to farmers that will help them increase their productivity. The offerings can be summarized in 6 different services i) Tillage scheduling, ii) Irrigation scheduling, iii) Crop growth monitoring, iv) Crop yield estimation, v) Weather forecasting (additional service) and vi) Management zones (additional service). Crop biomass is one of the biophysical parameters of crops that will be produced to support two of the services, namely crop growth monitoring and crop yield estimation. The services will be tested in three pilot areas: La Mancha (Spain), Pella (Greece) and Ruma (Serbia).

This deliverable consists of a set of User Guides and video tutorial and it is aimed to support the end-users in using the APOLLO platform beta version during beta pilot phase. The training material reflects the currently developed functionalities of APOLLO platform and will be updated in accordance with the further improvements of the platform.

2 Content of the training material

The current version of the APOLLO Training Material consists of:

- User Guide v1.0 (Appendix I)
 - Getting started
 - How to register...
 - How to log in ...
 - How to edit profile settings...
 - How to add parcels...
 - How to use the services...
- Video Tutorial v1.0
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0Bxno9IZrys9AVjZtTnBGSHE0MjA/view?usp=sharing>

Annex I: Get started with APOLLO

Get started with APOLLO services

Open APOLLO platform in your web browser (Chrome, Mozilla...). The address is: <http://apollo.draxis.gr> and follow the steps:

1st STEP
REGISTER AN APOLLO ACCOUNT

2nd STEP
LOG IN TO YOUR APOLLO ACCOUNT AND SET UP YOUR PROFILE

3rd STEP
ADD YOUR FIELDS

4th STEP
USE APOLLO SERVICES

Tillage Scheduling

Irrigation Scheduling

Crop Yield Estimation

Crop Growth Monitoring

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Annex II: User Guide “How to register an APOLLO account”

USER GUIDE

Version 1.0 - 24.10.2017.

HOW TO REGISTER AN APOLLO ACCOUNT...

Open APOLLO platform in your web browser (Chrome, Mozilla...). The address is: <http://apollo.draxis.gr>

Click on REGISTER pane

Fill in the requested information (e-mail, Name, Last name, password) and then click on REGISTER

A screenshot of a web browser window showing the registration page for Apollo. The browser address bar shows 'apollo.draxis.gr/register'. The form contains the following fields:

- EMAIL ADDRESS: farmerapollo@gmail.com
- NAME: Apollo
- LAST NAME: Farmer
- PASSWORD:
- CONFIRM PASSWORD:

A green button labeled 'REGISTER' is highlighted with a red box at the bottom of the form.

You received the Account Activation e-mail. Go to your e-mail account and open the e-mail received from APOLLO. Click on VERIFY YOUR EMAIL

New tab in your browser is opened. Click on here to complete your registration.

Annex III: User Guide “How to log in your APOLLO account”

USER GUIDE

Version 1.0 - 24.10.2017.

HOW TO LOG IN YOUR APOLLO ACCOUNT...

Insert the e-mail address and password set during registration

Log in

EMAIL ADDRESS
farmerapollo@gmail.com

PASSWORD

REMEMBER ME [Forgot password?](#)

LOG IN

Click on LOG IN

You are logged in your APOLLO account. Your APOLLO dashboard is now open.

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Annex IV: User Guide “How to edit profile settings”

USER GUIDE

Version 1.0 - 24.10.2017.

HOW TO EDIT PROFILE SETTINGS...

In the dashboard of your APOLLO account, click on your name

In the dropdown menu, click on View Profile

Edit your profile settings

Insert your phone number in order to receive notification by SMS

Screenshot of the Apollo Farmer profile settings page. The page shows the following fields and options:

- LAST NAME:** Farmer
- COUNTRY:** A dropdown menu is open, showing options: Greece (0030), Serbia (00381), and Spain (0034).
- PHONE NUMBER:** your phone number
- PREFERRED LANGUAGE:** English
- Buttons:** UPLOAD (green), UPDATE PROFILE (green)

When you finish editing, click on UPDATE PROFILE

Screenshot of the Apollo Farmer profile settings page. The page shows the following fields and options:

- LAST NAME:** Farmer
- COUNTRY:** Serbia (00381)
- PHONE NUMBER:** 123456789
- E-MAIL:** farmerapollo@gmail.com
- PREFERRED LANGUAGE:** English
- Buttons:** UPLOAD (green), UPDATE PROFILE (green, highlighted with a red box)

To change password, click on PASSWORD in the menu

Insert current password, new password and repeat new password

To edit settings for notification, click on NOTIFICATION in the menu

Set the frequency of notification

Set the way in which you would like to receive the notifications from APOLLO

Click on UPDATE PROFILE

Annex V: User Guide “How to add your parcels to APOLLO platform”

HOW TO ADD YOUR PARCELS TO APOLLO PLATFORM...

In the dashboard of your APOLLO account, click on +ADD A NEW PARCEL

Insert the information about the new parcel: name, crop type, irrigation system, sowing and harvesting dates

The screenshot shows the 'Add a new parcel' form in the Apollo web application. The form fields are as follows:

- PARCEL NAME:** Parcel 1 (highlighted with a red box)
- CROP TYPE:** WHEAT (selected in a dropdown menu)
- IRRIGATION SYSTEM:** IRRIGATION SPRINKLER (selected in a dropdown menu)
- SOWING DATE:** 10/15/2016
- HARVESTING DATE:** 07/08/2017

At the bottom of the form, there is a section labeled 'MARK YOUR FIELD LOCATION'.

Go to the map below and zoom in to the area where the parcel is situated

When you identify the parcel on the map, click on Draw a polygon symbol

By clicking over map, draw the parcel's boundaries

Click on the first point to close the polygon

Click on SAVE PARCEL. The new parcel is added to APOLLO.

Annex VI: User Guide “How to use APOLLO services”

USER GUIDE
Version 1.0 - 24.10.2017.

HOW TO USE APOLLO SERVICES...

List of the parcels added to APOLLO services is shown in the DASHBOARD of your APOLLO account, classified by CROP TYPES

CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	Tillage (2), Irrigation (1), Yield Estimation (%)
Wheat	14	1	47.87	Tillage (3), Irrigation, Yield Estimation (%)

YOUR CURRENT PLAN IS SILVER
Need a bigger plan? Apollo Gold gives you unlimited customers, parcels, crop types and more.

GET IN TOUCH

Click on a CROP TYPE (e.g. Maize) to list all the parcels with the crop type

Dashboard SHARE NP + ADD A NEW PARCEL

28 PARCELS **5** TILLAGE ALERTS **1** IRRIGATION ALERTS **% 0** YIELD ESTIMATION ALERTS

CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	2 1 %
Wheat	14	1	47.87	3 %

YOUR CURRENT PLAN IS SILVER
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Dashboard SHARE NP + ADD A NEW PARCEL

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CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	2 1 %

Maize

CUSTOMER	PARCEL ID	PARCEL NAME	HA	REGION	CURRENT CLIMATE	SERVICES
Nikola Paunovic	411	2_Iljija	3.29	Serbia	sunny	1 %
Nikola Paunovic	412	3_Duzine	2.65	Serbia	sunny	%

Click on the icon of the **Tillage service** for a parcel on the list

Tillage scheduling service for the chosen parcel is open and ready to use. In the upper part of the window, current weather and weather forecast for the next 6 days is displayed

In the lower part of the window, soil workability map is presented and a graph of timely change of temperature for a selected day

In the dropdown menu, select Soil Moisture option to display the data on the map.

Soil Moisture map is displayed

Switch to [Irrigation scheduling service](#) by clicking on the IRRIGATION tab in the services menu

By default, Irrigation Decision map is displayed.

The map shows one of the two possible information, namely Needs water or Does not need water

In the dropdown menu, select Irrigation dose to see precise amount of water needed.

Click on "Chrome Legacy Window" document in "Apollo"

The Irrigation dose is displayed on the map

Switch to [Crop Growth Monitoring service](#) by clicking on the CROP GROWTH MONITORING tab in the services menu

NDVI map is displayed by default. In the dropdown menu, chose another parameter (LAI, Chlorophyll content, biomass) to display

The selected parameter is displayed on the map

Switch to [Yield Estimation service](#) by clicking on the YIELD ESTIMATION tab in the services menu

Crop Yield map is displayed by default. In the dropdown menu, chose Crop Residues to display the map of residues

END OF DOCUMENT

